

Influence of Stock Market Dynamics, Renewable Energy Utilization, and Urban Development on Environmental Decline: Novel Insights from G20 Nations

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Abstract:

This study's main goal is to objectively investigate how stock market expansion, Urbanization FDI, and foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows affect CO2 emissions. This study also explores how the use of renewable energy affects CO2 emissions and economic output in a panel of G20 nations. The whole sample as well as sub-samples of rich and developing economies of the G20 member countries were used in the empirical analysis. The study tells that due to rise in urbanization the carbon dioxide emission reduced. Similarly, THE GDP growth and CO2 emission are positively related and our results shows that FDI and CO2 emission are also directly related. Meanwhile for the trade openness the results are mixed, in start it rises CO2 emission but after sometimes it reduces. Moreover, due to

shift of renewable energy consumption from fossil fuel helps to emit less CO2 and MSCI shows directly relation with CO2 emission for these countries. The findings support a notable long-run equilibrium link between the variables in all of the panels. Also, according to the long-run elasticities, FDI considerably lowers CO2 emissions in both the complete sample and emerging economies, while stock market growth declines in developed economies. Similar to how using renewable energy significantly lowers CO2 emissions and boosts economic output globally panels. Our conclusions have significant policy ramifications. In order to meet the rising demand for energy by displacing the usage of conventional energy sources like coal, gas, and oil, policymakers must first implement effective policies to promote renewable energy sources. As a result, both the CO2 emissions and the promotion of sustainable economic growth in the G20 nations will be aided. Also, according to the long-run elasticities, FDI

considerably lowers CO₂ emissions in both the complete sample and emerging economies, while stock market growth declines in developed economies.

Keywords: *Impact of Stock Market on Environment, Renewable energy Consumption and its impact on Environment, Urbanization on Environmental Degradation.*

Introduction

The word development has caused for many environmental problems. The states that have more industries or such kind of industrial activities have more chances to harm the environment and its inhabitants. These industries consume energy and emits the CO₂ that causes for global warming. The stock market index are related or linked with that countries. Although, government can play an important role by making strict policies regarding the recycling of waste gases (other material). But we can replace it with renewable energy resources. This use of renewable energy on CO₂ emission can impact positive relationship for economic growth. The utilization of renewable energy significantly lowers CO₂ emissions and boosts economic growth across. In order to meet the rising demand of energy by displacing the usage of conventional energy sources like coal, gas, and oil, policymakers must first implement effective policy by promoting renewable energy sources. This will help reduce CO₂ emissions and ensuring the G20 countries' sustainable economic growth (ReddyParamati, n.d.).

Environmental deterioration and CO₂ emissions are directly related to urbanization (Katircioğlu & Katircioğlu, 2017). The level of CO₂ emissions in Turkey was dramatically reduced as a result of urbanization. According to the study's findings, Turkey's urbanization development was not successfully handled in terms of "Green Energies and Green Environment." Our techniques can be replicated for the other nations that experienced fast urbanization for the purposes of comparison. As the many studies support that urbanization has positive relation with CO₂ emission and harm environment. But on the other hand, the studies shows negative relation between urbanization

and environmental quality. It also improve the quality of environment. According to several studies, there is a bad correlation between urbanization and carbon emissions. But, urbanization also improves resource efficiency, leading to an improvement in the quality of the environment. Lower environmental harm and effective service delivery are two advantages of denser urban areas, especially when they are accompanied by effective transportation networks and systems (with a focus on public transportation), efficient energy resource management systems, and effective waste management systems. In addition to safeguarding the lives and welfare of the populace, efficient energy resource utilization, and ultimately fostering green growth, it will keep African cities effective, manageable, resilient, and competitive.

The stock markets of a country usually directly relates with CO₂ emission of that country. Because, when the MSCI stock market index grow its industries and transport operations get faster. All these caused of CO₂ emission. But at some countries it negatively relate due to strict government policies (Younis et al., 2021). This shows that the MSCI stock market index price has a negative link to CO₂ emissions in Brazil but a positive association in India, Russia, China, and South Africa. Strong environmental restrictions and its enforcement by the Brazilian government may be one cause for this. The study also discovers a strong positive association between urbanization, foreign direct investment, and trade openness and CO₂ Emissions (Ma et al., 2022). Among the BRICS nations, the effect of stock market growth on environmental deterioration differs. Our findings have important policy ramifications. For instance, to fulfil the rising demand for energy by displacing the usage of conventional energy sources like

coal, gas, and oil, policymakers must implement effective measures to encourage renewable energy sources. We also see in our study that either it relates positively or negatively for G 20 countries.

FDI inflows, usage of renewable energy, and Carbon dioxide emission in the G20 countries. Previous studies in this field either concentrate on a certain nation or region. The results cannot be generalized in the absence of research on a larger sample of rich and emerging nations because their economic systems are very diverse from one another. When we extrapolate our results to both developed and developing nations, these discrepancies become more prominent. As a result of the lack of technological advancements in order to utilize renewable energy sources as well as the lack of capital necessary to implement advanced technology that may be necessary to use renewable energy sources, it is important to recognize that initial development in developing based on the use of fossil fuels. The results can be generalized by utilizing a larger sample of G20 nations, which includes developed and developing nations that are at various stages of development. Additionally, the G20 countries are important to the world economy because they produced more than 75percent of the global Gross domestic product and Carbon dioxide emission in 20122 (Paramati et al., 2016).

The study looks at the long- and short-term effects of using fossil fuels, foreign direct investment, and economic growth on CO2 emissions in 15 developing Asian nations. Additionally, the study argues that for the welfare of this region of the developing world, it will be beneficial to reduce overall fossil fuel consumption and support an ecologically friendly economic growth plan in these developing nations (Hanif et al., 2019).

The trade openness is consider beneficial for any economy but it has some negative impact on environment. Although, it helps to rise its GPA, grow exports and generates employment but it harms its environment in long term (Chukwudi & Nicholas, 2022). Due to its competitive advantage in the export and manufacturing of

items with high levels of pollution, South Africa has seen an influx of industries from industrialized nations, turning it into one of the world's "havens" for industries with high levels of pollution. This migration has greatly shifted pollution issues from these affluent countries to South Africa, which has significantly worsened the current environmental decline. South Africa continues to specialize in the creation of filthy goods, which significantly contribute to the degradation of her environmental quality, making it dirtier. South Africa has unavoidably become the world's most polluting factory as a result of commercial openness.

Literature Review

CO2 Emissions and urbanization

Studies have looked into the connection between urbanization's financial growth and CO2 Emissions on a global scale over the years. The outcomes are still not clear, though. On the other side, it was discovered that urbanization had a strong negative relationship with carbon emissions. On a sample of the Turkish economy, Katircioğlu and Katircioğlu, (2017) reported the same results on the relationship between urbanization and carbon emissions.

The western world to China, the findings indicated that urbanization has a large positive impact on carbon in the region emissions, however in eastern regions, where urbanization is going place quickly, it had little impact on carbon emissions. Since there was a significantly negative correlation between financial development and carbon emissions, it was discovered that it was slowing down environmental damage. The financial reforms for listed companies, which imply financial development, are the basis for this conclusion. It has been discovered that urbanization lowers carbon emissions. In order to reduce the rapid development in urbanization, governments in these countries are advised to spread knowledge.

Hypothesis: Urbanization has positive/negative effect on CO2 emission

CO2 Emissions and foreign direct investment

Caglar (2020) looks at nine nations ranked highest by the Climate Change Performance Index 2018 (CCPI) to analyse the relationship between carbon emissions, foreign direct investment, economic growth, and renewable and non-renewable energy sources. The results showed a significant long-term association between foreign direct investment in renewable energy and economic growth in several nations, although short-term outcomes were different for nine countries. The claimed justification for this was the variation in CO2 policy consequences across all nine countries. The CO2 Emission's is effected by FDI. Most of time foreign direct investment effect positively or negatively.

Hypothesis: FDI inflows have a positive effect on CO2 emissions.

CO2 Emissions and trade openness

A study by Alola (2019) in the USA found that trade, immigration, and monetary policy are the biggest barriers to environmental sustainability. They observed environmental deterioration factors in the USA between 1990 and 2018 for a different study. While migration and CO2 emissions were found to have a favorable relationship, the short-run results demonstrated a significant beneficial impact on CO2 emissions. In developing countries, Younis et al. (2021) investigate the connection between trade openness, FDI, and institutional performance on CO2 Emissions. The findings revealed a strong positive relationship between trade openness, FDI, and urbanization and environmental quality, but a significant negative relationship between institutional performance and ecological footprints.

The findings indicate that developing nations should adopt green technologies, clean production methods, and improved institutions for long-term environmental quality.

- CO2 Emissions and stock market price:

Studies have looked into the connection between global environmental degradation, energy use, and stock market financial development over the years. However, the findings are still not clear. Either a country's financial development results in increased energy consumption, which then carbon emissions leading to environmental damage or the opposite research on both mature and developing markets shown that carbon emissions are influenced by stock market indicators both developed and emergent markets are distinct. By choosing a US sample and Canadian markets, Paramati et al. (2016) investigated the effect of developed stock markets on environmental degradation. Efficient capital markets contribute to environmental performance by developing environmentally friendly rules and procedures for listed companies.

Hypothesis: Stock market developments have a positive impact on CO2 emissions.

CO2 Emissions and renewable energy

Boutabba (2020) examine the connection between CO2 Emissions and renewable energy in three European countries (France, the UK, and Germany). The reported link was also supported by robustness tests. The monthly relationship between the use of renewable energy and CO2 Emission's is examined by Sharif et al. (2020). The top 10 polluting nations in the world were used to choose the sample. The findings showed that, in contrast to India, Russia, and Indonesia, consumption of renewable energy is adversely correlated with environmental deterioration in China, the USA, Japan, Canada, Brazil, South Korea, and Germany. The government should adopt green energy policies as a replacement for outdated traditional energy sources in order to slow down ecological destruction. Paramati et al. (2016) investigate, in Tunisia, the EKC hypothesis's implications for the relationship between trade openness and green and non-green energy. Additionally, they discovered a one-way relationship between the use of green energy and carbon emissions. This relationship was

unidirectional and considerate of factors that were export- and import-oriented.

Hypothesis: The renewable energy consumption reduces CO2 emissions.

Table 1. Variables

Independent Variables:	Dependent variables:
1. Stock market index price (MSCI).	CO2 emissions
2. TEC Renewable energy proxy for total energy consumption	
3. Urbanization (UBR)	
4. FDI	
5. Trade Openness	

Materials and Methodology

Data Source and Detail about variables

To see the impact on CO2 emission due to GDP growth, Urbanization, FDI, TEC Renewable energy proxy for total energy consumption, Stock market index price (MSCI) and Trade openness (TO) of G20 countries. We get these data from Data Stream and World Development Indicator (WDI) from 1997 to 2021. The some data was missing of few variables of different countries. We have to eliminate those countries in order to get fair results of our research. We eliminate all those countries whose data is less than ten years. The remaining countries we have

to conduct our research with accurate and reliable data are ten. The data of Stock market index price (MSCI) of these countries was available from 1997 on Data stream. Further data about the variables of GDP growth, Urbanization, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), and Trade openness (TO) from the source of World Development Indicator (WDI). The data is easily accessible at this website (www.wdi.com). Similarly, the data of remaining two variables CO2 emission and TEC Renewable energy proxy for total energy consumption we get from data stream. This Morgan Stanley capital investment (MSCI)

When fossil fuels are burned, a process known as "combustion" releases carbon dioxide; this emission of Carbon dioxide is used as a stand-in for environmental destruction (MtCO2). GDP was calculated as GDP (constant 2010 US dollars), and energy consumption, which is calculated as total energy consumption, served as a proxy for renewable energy consumption (MTOE). Net of imports and exports serves as a proxy for foreign direct investment. The ratio of exports to imports as a percentage of GDP is used to measure trade openness. Urban growth is measured as urban population as a percent of the entire population. In China, the correlation between stock market prices and Emissions of carbon dioxide is depicted as having an inverse relationship, with stock prices declining as CO2 emissions rise.

Table 2. Table that Contains the Description about Variables

Variables Description	Unit of measurement	Source
CO2 emissions Carbon Dioxide from fossil fuels	Metric tons	Data stream
MSCI Morgan Stanley capital investment	US dollar	Data stream
TEC Renewable energy proxy for total energy consumption	Metric tons	Data stream
GDP Gross domestic products	Constant 2010 US\$	www.wdi.com
FDI Foreign direct investment	Net inflow of imports and exports	www.wdi.com
TO Trade openness	Percent of GDP	www.wdi.com
UBR Urbanization	Percent of total population	www.wdi.com

Econometrics Methodology

The secondary data about different variables are arranged in panel form. After that we apply

random effect and pooled model. The pooled model shows the relationship among different variables about all the countries under observance. The effect of GDP growth,

Urbanization, FDI, TEC Renewable energy proxy for total energy consumption, Stock market index price (MSCI) and Trade openness (TO) on CO2 emission. When we run the random effect and pooled model it tells us about different statistical values. The descriptive statistics different values we get about 158 observation of all the variables. Like, mean and standard deviation, minimum and maximum about the data. Similarly, we see its relationship of these variables. The R2 and adjusted R2 and their impact on this study. Adj-R2 for first is 0.6690, 0.6678, 0.6481, Housman (p-value) 0.9968. Similar to how using renewable energy significantly lowers CO2 emissions and boosts economic output globally panels. Our conclusions have significant policy ramifications. In order to meet the rising demand for energy by displacing the usage of conventional energy sources like coal, gas, and oil, policymakers must first implement effective policies to promote renewable energy sources. As a result, both the CO2 emissions and the promotion of sustainable economic growth in the G20 nations will be aided. Also, according to the long-run elasticities, FDI considerably lowers CO2 emissions in both the complete sample and emerging economies, while stock market growth declines in developed economies. The study's findings will add significantly to the corpus of knowledge and have substantial policy ramifications for the G20 countries.

Generalized method of moment model

The relationship between MSCI stock exchange development, FDI, GDP, trade openness (TO), TEC renewable energy, urbanization, and carbon dioxide emissions is examined in this study. It treats MSCI stock exchange development, FDI, GDP, trade openness (TO), TEC renewable energy, urbanization, as predictor variables, while environmental pollution (CO2 emission) is treated as an outcome variable.

Result Analysis

The table on descriptive statistics provides an overview of all study variables. All of the

variables, urbanization was determined to become the least volatile. The differences between MSCI, TO, FD, and GDP are negligible. Compared to CO2 and GDP2, these GDP2 appears to have the largest volatility, with a variance that is roughly twice as high as all other variables. Table 4 displays the correlation matrix between the various factors. With a value of 0.9726, Tec has the strongest positive correlation, while GDP2 has a score of 1.000, GDP is 0.776, FD is 0.549, and EOP is 0.3736. However, MSCI and URB have a correlation with values of 0.093 and 0.212, respectively.

This study shows that overall, due to rise in urbanization caused to reduce in CO2 emission. This result shows that due to urbanization the pollution of carbon dioxide reduced. The one of the reason can be that the people who comes toward offices in the cities use personal transport, to their children traveled through vehicle to get education, patients have come to hospital for treatment and they have to travel to the cities for various purposes. All were caused to emit more CO2 individually but when they migrated to cities they migrated to cities this CO2 emission reduced. Now their offices, schools, hospitals and other necessities are near to their homes. They have to use least transport as compare to earlier. In addition to this, Due to GDP growth the CO2 emission increase. Because, GDP of any country is directly linked to its industrial growth that leads more combustion process not only in industries but also in the transportation. All these are directly related and our research support this in these countries. Further, our results shows that FDI and CO2 emission is directly related. As more investment come in the state the more projects starts that finally contribute to emits more carbon dioxide in the environment. Meanwhile for the trade openness the results are mixed, in start in rise CO2 emission but after sometimes it reduces. Moreover, due to shift of renewable energy consumption from fossil fuel helps to emit less CO2. There is positive relation between renewable energy consumption and carbon emission. The reason behind this is very simple, when they get energy through steam and combustion process that exhaust CO2 but now

people shifts it to solar energy that is environment friendly. Finally, the Morgan and

Stanly Capital investment have directly relation with CO2 emission for these countries.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Observation	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ICO2	158	1.752	.646	1.055	3.557
GDP	158	7.362	.949	5.493	9.514
Urb	158	4.306	.132	3.91	4.519
FDI	158	3.077	1.502	-3.355	7.298
TO	158	5.53	.822	.693	6.213
RE	158	2.247	.818	-.357	3.55
MSCI	158	3.581	.422	2.168	4.246

Table 4. Matrix of Correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
ICO2	1.000						
GDP	0.776	1.000					
Urb	0.212	0.447	1.000				
FDI	0.549	0.675	0.135	1.000			
TO	-0.086	-0.045	-0.084	0.271	1.000		
RE	-0.089	-0.040	-0.442	0.230	0.235	1.000	
MSCI	0.093	-0.130	0.077	-0.110	-0.091	-0.348	1.000

Table 5. The Pooled Model, the Fixed Effects (FE) and the Random Effects (RE) Parameter Estimates

Variable	Pooled	Fixed	RE
GDP	.59514735***	.78885502***	.77562648***
Urb	-1.1966193***	-1.5185078***	-1.4924947***
FDI	0.019	-0.008	-0.008
TO	-0.030	-0.003	-0.003
RE	-0.076	-.18493196***	-.18331099***
MSCI	.29678003***	0.019	0.021
_cons	1.739	2.8708944**	2.8548771***
Observation			
Adj-R ²	0.6690	0.6678	0.6481
Housman (p-value)	0.9968		

Legend: * p<0.05; ** p<0.01; *** p<0.001

Discussion

This study investigates the impact of urbanization, MSCI, trade openness, foreign direct investment, and renewable energy on CO2 Emissions. In order to do this, we estimate the panel root test, which supports the macro panel's findings. The panel root test addresses non-stationarity and disproves the homogeneity

presumption. It aids in recognizing the cross-dependence of variables as you work with panel data. It may be inferred from this that FDI inflows into emerging economies bring cutting-edge energy efficiency technologies, environmentally friendly technology, and advances in the industrial processes, all of which contribute to the economies' reduced CO2

emissions. The established economies, however, are not dependent on FDI inflows for the transfer of knowledge, and it is possible that these economies turned these FDI inflows into industrial activities without paying much attention to emission management. Therefore, we advocate that both developed and developing from the panels, hence we advise the leaders of those nations to implement strong policies to raise the proportion of renewable energy consumption in overall energy use. The use of renewable energy also has a huge positive impact on the economic output across the panels, and this may be achieved by stimulating significant domestic and foreign investments in renewable energy projects as well as supporting PPP investments. This suggests that using renewable energy has a beneficial effect on the economy growth. This guarantees long-term economic growth. In order to encourage the use of renewable energy, policymakers must change their incentives for conventional energy. Additionally, the results support the one-way causality between stock market growth and GDP per capita in developing economies as well as the strong positive feedback relationship between stock market capitalization and economic growth in the complete sample and developed economies.

Conclusion and Policy Implications

The current discussion in both developed and emerging economies is how to reduce CO₂ emissions without slowing down the pace of economic growth. Both corporations and policymakers struggle to strike this fine balance. Energy consumption is rising across all industries, but regrettably, the main energy sources remain fossil fuels like coal, gas, and oil. However, the developed economies have made tremendous strides in raising the amount of clean and renewable energy in total energy use. In developing economies, where fossil fuels make up more than 70% of energy use, it is still a significant problem. Therefore, it is crucial for policymakers to come up with alternative solutions to lower CO₂ emissions and boost the proportion of renewable energy in overall energy

country policymakers start implementing measures to redirect FDI inflows toward clean and renewable energy projects. As a result, this will aid in achieving sustainable economic growth in all of these economies. Given that using renewable energy has grave environmental consequences Influence on the CO₂ emissions

consumption. This study, which was inspired by the patterns of global energy consumption, looked at how stock market growth and FDI inflows affected CO₂ emissions as well as how consumption of renewable energy affected both CO₂ emissions and economic output across panels of the full sample, developed and developing economies of the G20. The empirical findings of this study imply that the variables have a significant long-run equilibrium relationship. This suggests that, over time, stock market capitalization, FDI inflows, and consumption of renewable energy are all substantially correlated with CO₂ emissions. In a similar vein, long-term usage of renewable energy is closely related to economic output. The long-run CO₂ emission elasticities showed that FDI inflows have a positive and negative impact on the CO₂ emissions of established and developing countries, respectively, whereas stock market development has a positive and negative impact. The empirical findings of this study imply that the variables have a significant long-run equilibrium relationship. This suggests that, over time, stock market capitalization, FDI inflows, and consumption of renewable energy are all substantially correlated with CO₂ emissions. In a similar vein, long-term usage of renewable energy is closely related to economic output. The long-run CO₂ emission elasticities showed that FDI inflows have a positive and negative impact on the CO₂ emissions of established and developing countries, respectively, whereas stock market development has a positive and negative impact. The findings also support the notion that while renewable energy reduces CO₂ emissions across developed and emerging nations in the G20, non-renewable energy contributes to higher emissions of that gas. In comparison to industrialized economies, the impact of using renewable energy on economic output is substantially greater in

developing countries. We derive the crucial policy implications from these findings. The ability of stock markets to reduce CO₂ emissions must be recognized by policymakers. To ensure that all the listed companies implement energy-efficient and environmentally friendly technologies in their industrial activities, policymakers must create effective and sustainable policies. Even privately held businesses that are not publicly traded will receive significant signals about the state of the economy from stock markets. In addition, by offering lucrative investment incentives and by fostering a positive business environment for the investing community, policymakers should start initiatives to use these constantly expanding stock markets to finance clean and renewable energy projects.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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